

OF THE ROLE OF INFORMATION AND INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGY IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

Today, it is not possible to imagine the improvement of any industry without both information and communication technologies and innovations. One of the most common tasks is using cutting-edge technologies, as well as, introducing innovations in the area, especially, amongst upbringing of young generation. This article involves the importance of information technologies in arranging the system of preschool education by using today's requirements, improving the effectiveness of education in raising a healthy child and mature in all areas, and the organization of preschool education in the society of modern information which both pedagogues and students' parents put essential tasks to accomplish.

Today's considerably developing information system involves all sphere of society, besides the sphere of education. PF -5349 dated February 19, 2018 and PF - 6079 dated February 19, 2018 and PF - 6079 dated October 5, 2020 "On making measurement to further incline the information technologies and communications" of the President of Uzbekistan "Digital Uzbekistan 2030" Decree No 3549 dated February 19, 2018 "On the organization of the activities of the Ministry of Informational Technologies and Communications Development in the Republic of Uzbekistan. According to this decision, since in other fields of our society, the widely use of information technologies and communications in the process of education is being one of the

devices to make sure the education quality in the area of preschool education.

Introducing of information, as well as communication technologies to the areas of preschool education that primary step of education, gets huge responsibility on the pedagogical issues, demands them to get their act together and build up the level of knowledge about ICT and their activeness and imagination.

Both information and communication technologies in the system of preschool education expects the following results while using it:

Firstly, stimulating of the education quality in preschool education, and also the effect of preparing children for school.

Secondly, expanding children's free thinking and viewpoint to the world.

Thirdly, rising the level of intellectual, social - emotional and creative improvement of youngsters .

It is essential to make powerful the cooperation between parents and the organization of preschool education to provide convenience.

Fully equipped with gadgets , full of exhibition mornings ,events and circle classes on educating foreign languages obtains a beneficial effect on the improvement of child's talent and ability. In fact , the possibilities of information technologies, as well as innovations get a positive effect on the mental and intellectual development of pupils. A person who is 6-7 years old is able to use information and communication tools such as cell phone, tablet laptop, etc... Additionally, using these kinds of correctly is sending to a school that gives an opportunity to use the basement of modern technologies, advance information technologies, be physically ready by gaining necessary intellectual skills and be psychologically prepared.

During informational process, it is being the most important task to adequately equip the preparator group rooms in the preschool education organization, to find a solution the problems of adaptation for multimedia equipment, and to stimulate the literacy of the ICT of the pedagogical staff working in the organization of preschool education .

Using both information and communication technologies in the preschool education system is expressed in various ways:

- a) using these technologies while educating children online in educational process.
- b) using these technologies accompanying by parents and pedagogues.

c) using these technologies while working with teachers to stimulate the quality of education.

Today's modern societies put several tasks for pedagogues of preschool education organization. Firstly, the pedagogue should pay her attention the way of choosing computer games and educational programs by selecting her pupil. That is way , it is essential for the educator to know computer literacy , as well as be able to use effectively the resources of the global internet network properly during educational activities by conducting with preschool age children.

In the life of preschool child players one of the most beneficial role , and it obtains huge importance for the forming and improving a child's personality. Looking at the computer games, the child age of educational games should provide compliance with moral standarts. Using multimedia in preschool education gets beneficial effects on the improvement of the child's mentality and creativity besides stimulating the effectiveness of educating children . In the Paint program, the child select colours for the items, creatures , natural scenery or uses them in place, and as a consequence improves his work, individual personality , and interest. They are more beneficial than drawing ordinary paper. Meanwhile, ICT as a means of interactive education permits the child to gain quickly discovered knowledge and expand his point of view. These interactive computer games have to created by the educator by depending on the state requirements in the Power Point program and to play with children during the training . For instance, in the activity center of the game , such as , " Let's build a building", " Find the difference", " What's

missing ", " Find the mistake ", " we dress up the doll ", " Place the shape ", " Paint the picture" ,while playing games with aid of animated images , the child learns the information with huge interest.

If we make a comparison between computerized pedagogical technologies and traditional forms of education in the preschool education. The illustration of the information on the screen computer in a game form raises children's attention and intrerst in this kind of activity, images of movement, sound , as well as multiplication remaine a long - lasting impression the child's memory. Putting issues and solving them by a computer has an effective effect on the stimulation of children's ability to think more logically.

As given in the judgement of preschool education of the Republic of Uzbekistan,a computer gives a chance for a specialized approach to the child , while this process every children will manage to complete the task by basing on their intellectual positions and personalities. However ,it is urgent to make formation children's skills to use computers and cellphones correctly, to think about not only positive activities, but also negative ones. It is soly highlights effective educational and should bring to

ensure its modernity. Another striking problem is that introducing ICT to preschool education is not sufficient competence of pedagogical task in the area of cutting -edge information technologies. Modern pedagogues are essential to work independently on stimulating their knowledge and skills day by day.

All in all , it should be considered that both information and communication technologies are used in organizing the pedagogical process in the preschool education system,in provision of continuous methodical services , in organizing of the methodical activities of teachers and medical employees , and handle to manage other specialists activities, to carry out accurately whole monitoring system . On the other hand , there have several problems. This kind of process demands huge responsibility from both pedagogues and parents. Togetherly, they make sure to use information and communication technologies correctly for the comprehensive improvement of the child.Finally ,the most common task of today is to supply the quality of education and upbringing the youngsters from the first step.

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